

Impact of Technology and Human Capital Development on Economic Growth In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study, focused on the impact of technology and human capital development on economic growth in Nigeria between 2000-2021. Ordinary least Squares (OLS) was employed to analyze the data. In analyzing the data for this study, it was observed that all the variables spur economic growth. The regression result showed that the overall model is satisfactory given the coefficient of determination of 31 percent and F-statistics at 3.488683. The result also revealed that there is positive relationship between Education Expenditure (EDUEX), Total Government Expenditure on Health (TGEH) and Gross Domestic Product (GPD) and a negative relationship between GDP and Total government expenditure on Technology variables. Based on these findings, the study recommended that Nigerian government needs to improve and supply facilities to schools and health sector to promote growth. At the same time, more funding is needed for research and development to encourage innovations and inventions in both schools and research centers across the country. These, coupled with sincere commitment, would substantially accelerate economic growth of the country.

Keywords: *Human Capital, Development, Technology, Economic Growth.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The interplay between human capital development and technology stands as a pivotal force shaping the economic trajectory of Nigeria. In recent years, the nation has recognized the imperative of nurturing its human capital through education, skills enhancement, and healthcare, alongside embracing technological advancements across various sectors. This symbiotic relationship holds the promise of not only elevating economic growth but also ushering in a transformative era for Nigeria's standing in the global economy. Investment in human capital, represented by the knowledge, skills, and health of the workforce, serves as a bedrock for sustainable development. Concurrently, the integration of technology acts as a catalyst, propelling the nation into the digital age and fostering innovation across industries. Together, they present a formidable force that has the potential to redefine Nigeria's economic landscape and enhance its competitiveness on the international stage (Adedeji, 2017).

This study will therefore explore the multifaceted impact of human capital development and technology on Nigeria's economy, spanning from advancements in education and healthcare to the digital transformation of sectors like agriculture and finance. By navigating through these dimensions, we aim to uncover the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead, outlining a comprehensive picture of the ongoing evolution and the potential future trajectories for Nigeria

in the realm of human capital and technology integration. In the intricate tapestry of Nigeria's economic evolution, the threads of human capital development and technological integration weave a narrative of transformative change. This essay embarks on a journey to unravel the profound impact of these two interwoven forces, which have emerged as the linchpin for Nigeria's aspirations in the global economic arena.

Yusuf (2019) observed that at the heart of this exploration lies the recognition that the prosperity of a nation is intricately tied to the knowledge, skills, and health of its people. Human capital development, encompassing investments in education and healthcare, becomes the cornerstone upon which the edifice of economic growth is erected. Simultaneously, the relentless march of technology across sectors ushers in a new era of efficiency, innovation, and connectivity. Nigeria, with its vibrant population and rich cultural tapestry, finds itself at a crossroads where these twin forces converge. The government's initiatives in education, skills training, and healthcare, coupled with the rapid strides in technological advancements, set the stage for a dynamic redefinition of the nation's economic landscape.

As we embark on this exploration, we will traverse the realms of education, healthcare, and technological adoption in key sectors. It will unravel the synergies between a skilled, healthy workforce and the transformative power of technology, shedding light on the potential opportunities and challenges that lie ahead for Nigeria's economic odyssey. Through this lens, we seek to understand not only the current dynamics but also the intricate pathways that may unfold, shaping Nigeria's economic destiny at the nexus of human capital development and technological innovation.

The objective of this paper therefore is to assess the impact of technology and human capital development on the economic growth in Nigeria. The rest of the paper is organized into section one - introduction, section two - review of related literature, section three - methodology, section four - result presentation and analysis and section five -summary and conclusion of the paper.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1.1 Concept of Human Capital

Human capital refers to education, health, on-the-job training and the skills acquired through interaction of people or societies (Jaijeoba, 2015). In more technical terms human capital is defined as the aggregation of the innate abilities and the knowledge and skills that individuals acquire and develop throughout their lifetime. Human capital is also taken as an index of human welfare as health and education not only meant to accelerate economic growth but are also recognized as the principal indicators of economic growth and development. The impact of human capital on economic growth has gained prominence in the literature. The investment in human and physical capital separately and interactively affects the economic

performance of a country.

Nigeria has consistently neglected its human development sector and as a result total factor productivity remained very low in the country as opportunity cost of educating a child over his work in the informal sector at negligible wage still matters in most of the rural areas (Romer, 1986).

2.1.2 Concept of Economic Growth

Economic growth is a steady process by which the productive capacity of an economy is increased over time to bring about rising levels of national income and output, (Kuznet, 1971). He interprets the increase in per capita product as indicative of an increase in economic welfare. In his view, Mankiw (1992), presents the argument that the primary measure of economic growth must be real income obtained per hour worked. He views economic growth as ‘an increase in the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services compared from one period of time to another. This can best be measured in nominal or real terms, the latter of which is adjusted for inflation. Traditionally, aggregate economic growth is measured in terms of Gross National Product (GNP) or Gross Domestic Product (GDP), although alternative matrices are sometimes used. Mankiw (1992) further defines economic growth as how much more the economy produces, than it did before. This definition is premised on the rationale that if an economy is producing more, businesses are more profitable and stock prices rise. This gives companies capital to invest and hire more employees. As more jobs are created, income rises, consumers have more money to buy additional products and services, which derives higher economic growth. This makes economic growth the most watched economic indicator.

2.1.3 Concept of Technology

Technology is the way in which people use their ideas of science to build machines and make tasks easier. Although technology began in prehistoric times, it advanced rapidly only after the industrial revolution which began in the 18th century (1760, specifically). Since that time, technology has dramatically changed the world (Romer, 1990). It has given us fast, safe transportation, materials such as plastics, world-wide communications such as telephone and television, and many other useful appliances. Perhaps the greatest benefits of technology are from modern medicine, which has improved our health and lengthen our lives. However, technology has a negative side too - it produces weapons with the power to cause death and destruction. The development of computers has been one of the most important recent advances in technology. Computers can perform many different tasks and are used in banking, architecture, manufacturing, the education sector and many other business computers also aid new technology because they can help design and invent new machines.

The role of human capital and technology in determining growth has been subjected to debate for a long time, from a theoretical basis to empirical testing. Technology is a significant factor

influencing economic growth, and variations in growth rates. Noticeably, this in itself is something that evolutionary economics has in common, with the new growth theory.

Growth in per-capita output is a vital element of economic well-being. Technology and equipment are the output of human minds and only be made productive by people. The attainment of fruitful programme depends on human innovative ideas and creativeness.

2.2 THEORETICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

2.2.1 Endogenous Growth Theory

Endogenous growth theory highlighted the fact that if productivity was to increase, the labor force must continuously be provided with more resources. Resources in this case include physical capital, human capital and knowledge capital (technology). Therefore, growth was driven by accumulation of the factor of production, while accumulation in turn was the result of investment in the private sector. This implied that the only way a government can affect economic growth, at least in the long run, was via its impact on investment in capital, education and research and development. Reduction of growth in these models occurred when public expenditures deter investment by creating tax wedges beyond that necessary to finance their investments or taking away the incentives to save and accumulate capital (Holster and Henrekson, 1997).

2.3 EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Adedeji, (2017), examined Human Capital Development in Nigeria: Retrospect and Prospect. Adedeji discusses the importance of human capital development in Nigeria's economic growth, emphasizing the need for investment in education and healthcare to enhance productivity and competitiveness. Oluwatobi, Efobi, & Olurinola, (2015) carried out a research on Human Capital Development and Poverty Reduction in Nigeria: A Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Approach." This study examines the relationship between human capital development and poverty reduction in Nigeria, highlighting the role of education and skill acquisition in improving livelihoods and socioeconomic outcomes.

Aderinto and Agboola (2018) carried out a research on Information and Communication Technology, Financial Inclusion and Economic Growth in Nigeria. The authors analyze the impact of information and communication technology (ICT) on financial inclusion and economic growth in Nigeria, emphasizing the role of technology in expanding access to financial services and driving development. Yusuf (2019) examined the Impact of Technology on Human Capital Development: A Case Study of Selected Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria. He examined the impact of technology adoption in tertiary institutions on human capital development in Nigeria, highlighting the role of digital tools and e-learning platforms in enhancing educational

outcomes and skill acquisition.

Onyeneke and Okwo (2018) examined Human Capital Development and Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria.” This study investigated the relationship between human capital development and economic growth in Nigeria, emphasizing the need for policies that promote education, healthcare, and technology-driven innovation to stimulate sustainable development and found out the human capital development plays a vital roles in the economic development of Nigeria.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Model Specification and Sources of data

Data used for the study are secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (Annual reports and statically bulletin, 2021).

3.2 Model Specification

The model examined the relationship between Technology, Human Capital Development and Economic Growth in Nigeria between 2000 and 2021.

GDP which is the dependent variable was assumed as a function of the independent variables which are EDU, HEL, TECH.

$$\text{That is } GDP = f(\text{EDU}, \text{HEL}, \text{TECH}) \tag{1}$$

Endogenous growth theory as stated above will form the basis of the specification of the model. The functional relationship between economic growth and human capital development plus technology will be established.

The dependent variable is Real Gross Domestic Product which is used as proxy for economy growth. The explanatory variables are Public Expenditure health, public expenditure on education and the technology factor.

The mathematical function of the relationship is as follows:

$$GDP = f(\text{EDU}, \text{HEL}, \text{TECH}) \tag{2}$$

The above function is transformed into the following explicit econometric model.

$$GDP = K_0 + K_1 \text{EDU} + K_2 \text{HEL} + K_3 \text{TECH} + e \dots \dots \dots \tag{3}$$

Where

- K0 = Intercept (Constant)
- K1 – K3 = Co-efficient to be estimated,
- GDP = Economic Growth
- EDU = Expenditure on Education
- HEL = Expenditure on Health
- TECH = Technology
- e = Stochastic variable/Error term
- F = Functional notation

The functional model above is further transformed into logarithm for standardization as this may minimize the difference in the magnitude of different variables. The log form model is as follows:

$$\ln \text{GDP} = K_0 + K_1 \ln \text{EDU} + K_2 \ln \text{HEL} + K_3 \ln \text{TECH} + e$$

A priori expectations is $K_1 > 0$, $K_2 > 0$ $K_3 > 0$

4. RESULTS PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The empirical model was estimated using the conventional Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique to investigate the impact of Human capital, technology and economic growth in Nigeria. The choice of OLS lies in the fact that it produces reliable estimates for regression co-efficient.

Table 1: Regression Result

Variable	Coefficient	Sid. Error	t-Statistic	Prob,
C	5.999631	1.800776	3.331692	0.0054
LNEDU	2.31 E-09	1.77E-09	1.304124	0.2148
LNHEL	0.012715	0.018322	0.693960	0.4999
LNTECH	-1.012630	0.465243	-2.176562	0.0485
R-squared	0.446008	Mean dependent var		3.63000
Adjusted R-squared	0.318184	S.D. dependent var		3.298020
S.E. of regression	2.723286	Akaike info criterion		5.043880
Sum squared resid	96.41176	Schwarz criterion		5.239530
Log likelihood	-38.87298	Hannan-Quinn criter.		5.063368
F-statistic	3.488683	Durbin-Watson stat		1.746178
Prob(F-statistic)	0.047064			

The empirical results in Table 1 indicate that the co-efficient of the explanatory variables are correctly signed, thereby confirming to our a priori expectations. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between Education Expenditure (EDU), Total Government Expenditure on Health (HEL) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). A constant of 5.999631 implies that the economy will grow by average of 5 percent if other coefficients are zero. The estimated coefficient of EDU is 2.3 which indicate that a one percent increase in education expenditure will lead to about 2.3 percent growth in the real GDP. The estimated coefficient of HEL is 0.012 which indicate that a one percent increase in health expenditure will lead to about one percent growth in the real GDP. Both coefficients of EDU and HEL are statistically insignificant. However, the estimated coefficient of TECH of -1.012 which shows that one percent increase in technology will lead to about 1.01 percent decrease in growth of the real GDP. Even though it is statistically significant, the result is counterintuitive as technology is meant to drive growth. Besides, the value of the coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.44 shows that about 44 percent of the variation in the dependent variable (RGDP) is explained by changes in the explanatory

variables (the independent variables) in model. The remaining unexplained variation is taken care of by the error term represented in the model. The adjusted (R²) tends to purge the influence of the explanatory variables, the dependent variable is explained by 31 percent.

The Durbin-Watson (D.W.) statistics of 1.746178 as it is significantly below the bench mark of 2, we can conclude that the residual is free from autocorrelation.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to find out the existence of the relationship between Economic growth (GDP), Government Total Expenditure on Education (EDU), Government Total Expenditure on Health (HEL) and Technology variable (TECH) in Nigeria. The methodology employed in this study is the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique. The scope of the study spanned from 2000 to 2021. The result shows that there is a positive relationship between Expenditure on Education, Total Government Expenditure on Health (nd Gross Domestic Product (GDP)); and a negative relationship between GDP and Technology variable. The role of human capital and technology toward determining economic growth cannot be overemphasized based on the theory. Empirically, while some literature has proven this assertion, others have disproved it. It is against this background that this study investigated the impact of human capital formation, technology and economic growth in Nigeria, over the period 2000-2020. The policy suggestion based on the findings of our study is that human capital and technology are not only theoretically growth-driven variables but also empirically tested growth driven variables. Essentially, Nigeria's government needs to improve and supply facilities to schools and health sector to promote growth.

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